

Home / Comic Reviews / Graphic Fiction / Thirst as Ecological Distress: Planetary Health and Water Scarcity in Brenda Larusso's Cánidos [Canines]

Thirst as Ecological Distress: Planetary Health and Water Scarcity in Brenda Larusso's Cánidos [Canines]

Facebook Twitter Pinterest

Author: Brenda Larusso
Format: Paperback
Pages: 133
Publish Date: 2024
Publisher: Fondo de Cultura Económica (Country: Mexico)
Catalog ID: ISBN: 978-6071684233
Where to buy: <https://elfondoonline.com/detalle.aspx?ctit=054027R>
Author website: www.linktr.ee/metrofanzine

Search this site...

Subscribe to the Graphic Medicine Newsletter

Join our email list to keep up with the latest Graphic Medicine news!

Enter email address ...

Sign Up

Syllabus Repository

NEW! Click on the image below to explore graphic medicine syllabi for undergraduate, graduate, and health professional courses.

Review

by Dr. [Velebita Koričančić](#), Mexico City

A dehydrated ecosystem appears as an illness affecting the collective body in [Brenda Larusso's Cánidos \(2024\)](#), published by the Fondo de Cultura Económica after the book won Mexico's National Young Graphic Novel Award in 2022.^[1] Dedicated poignantly "To those who have experienced thirst," *Cánidos* ("Canidae" or "Canines") is an almost wordless narrative of drought and forced migration, but also survival, offering a striking intervention in contemporary Latin American sequential art. With text limited largely to paratextual elements (the title, chapter numbers, and back-cover synopsis), *Cánidos* uses the comics page to address ecological crisis. Set in an eco-dystopian landscape, the narrative frames thirst as an individual experience that demands a communal response.

Read through the lens of "[planetary health](#)," an interdisciplinary field that examines how [human and more-than-human bodies depend on healthy natural systems](#).^[2] *Cánidos* shows how water scarcity registers in bodies, communities, and landscapes alike. After a village of anthropomorphic canines selects a young coyote to search for water, their journey leads to encounters with other canines (a fox, a dog, and a magical jackal), all of whom are suffering from the drought. The story ends with a truce grounded in solidarity, though its open ending refuses easy resolution.

By giving visual form to water scarcity as a planetary-health crisis, the comic foregrounds that all active life is dependent on water. In this sense, *Cánidos* insists visually on ecological crisis through the slow wearing down of the traveling body. For instance, the young coyote balances buckets from a pole across their shoulders, dragging tools, and later unfolds a map, as if orientation itself has become difficult in the emptied terrain. They

walk with a lowered head and then pause beside dry plants, only to collapse after cactus spines pierce them. This cactus scene is significant because the environment itself injures them; the landscape enters the body as pain.^[ii] As the environment is increasingly depleted and bodies grow ever so exhausted, ecological distress imprints as a sick collective body.

Through recurring water-related motifs, such as containers, dry wells, desert landscapes, and routes, the narrative foregrounds scarcity as both narrative setting and material condition. To search for water in *Cánidos* is to follow a story of displacement caused by climate collapse, where movement is required in order to adapt to ecological loss. What is especially relevant is that the animal characters collaborate here rather than compete for survival. This challenges the all-too-common assumption that scarcity must lead to conflict. Instead, the narrative imagines survival as a multispecies alliance when it insists that communities can resist only together.

Cánidos matters to Graphic Medicine when it orients the field's attention toward environmental illness as well as highlighting the conditions required for survival amid ecological collapse. Because the comic does not rely on verbal explanation, it evokes the physical toll of dehydration through bodily representation. When speech is stripped away and survival reduces characters to their silent materiality, *Cánidos* shows how graphic narratives envision planetary health as indeed embodied and emotionally resonant for survival of all living beings.

Dr. Velebita Koričančić (ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2941-1471>) is a Croatian professor-researcher, born in Zagreb and based in Mexico City. She holds a Master's degree in Latin American Studies, *cum laude*, from the University of Salamanca, Spain, and a PhD in Comparative Literature, with honors, from the National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM). She is an Assistant Professor at Anahuac Mexico University's School of Communication and an Adjunct Professor in the Department of Latin American Studies at UNAM's School of Philosophy and Letters. She is also a Candidate-level member of Mexico's National System of Researchers and a literary translator.

^[i] Mexico's National Young Graphic Novel Award is given for an unpublished manuscript, and the recipient's work is subsequently published.

^[ii] Whitmee, Sarah, et al. "Safeguarding Human Health in the Anthropocene Epoch: Report of The Rockefeller Foundation–Lancet Commission on Planetary Health." *The Lancet*, vol. 386, n° 10007, 2015, pp. 1973–2028.

^[iii] This narrative circumstance, in which an anthropomorphic canine becomes unable to survive in nature, is reminiscent of John Steinbeck's "Flight," a story in which a human protagonist likewise becomes unable to survive in nature. [Kevin Wolf, Review Editor for *Graphic Medicine*](#), suggested this parallel to *Cánidos* as a parable about climate change, in a personal communication, June 3, 2026.

Leave a Comment

Comment *

Name *

Email *

Website

Post Comment

This site uses Akismet to reduce spam. [Learn how your comment data is processed.](#)

© 2007 - 2026 Graphic Medicine International Collective

WordPress Developer